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Introduction

Mentoring is an effective intervention for undergraduates that increases retention, professional identity, and grades (Crisp et al., 2017). Formal mentorship is a practice that takes various forms in undergraduate education. Undergraduate research, for example, often relies on faculty-student mentorship to enhance learning experiences (Johnson et al., 2015). Student affairs is another home for student mentoring programs targeted at special groups of students, for example mentoring women, minority, or first-generation students (Crisp & Cruz, 2009, p. 530). Yet mentoring is rarely embedded in a class, perhaps because the professor must act as both teacher and program administrator. We know there are also limited incentives for faculty members to engage in mentoring of undergraduates (Baker, et al., 2015).

Mentorship facilitates a learning experience. Scholars have differentiated inquiry-based learning from undergraduate research and problem-based learning (Spronken-Smith, 2010). Inquiry based learning is an experience that leads to new knowledge and is guided by a question, facilitated by a faculty member, self-directed, and action oriented.

This paper examines how an optional mentoring program provided an inquiry learning experience for students in course *Leading Underserved Communities*. We take a dialogue approach to examine the implementation and the experience of mentorship as an inquiry-based learning experience about rural leadership. The rationale for and description of the program are presented first. Two students (EP and JB) and a faculty member (LL) take a dialogue approach to share our perspectives. Challenges and concerns are summarized before concluding with recommendations for others.

Rural Leadership Mentoring Program

The Rural Leadership Mentoring (RLM) program was part of a course *Leading Underserved Communities* in the spring semester of 2021. The course was offered at a private, liberal arts university, located in a rural NC county. Preparing students to “lead with purpose” is part of the university mission. The course was the second course in a series of three courses, which were designed to increase student engagement in rural communities. The idea for mentoring came from a conversation LL had with the university president. He asked LL, who studies mentorship, if it might be possible to have students in the course experience mentoring?

LL felt it was important that participation in the mentoring program be optional. The mentoring program was designed to align with course assignments, this alignment is described in more detail below. A month before class started LL surveyed enrolled students to ask if they wanted a

mentor. Two-thirds ($n = 10$) of the students indicated they did want a mentor and they provided their name, hometown county, and sector interest.

During the fall of 2020, LL partnered with the NC Rural Center to identify mentors. The NC Rural Center's mission is to improve the quality of life for rural North Carolinians. The center runs a successful Rural Leadership program and staff agreed to recruit potential mentors from the program alumni. The staff asked that students indicate what sectors were of most interest: elected office, health, education, government, non-profit, faith, agriculture, or no preference. This information, along with the student's hometown, were used to match mentees and mentors. Each student who requested a mentor was matched with one by the NC Rural Center.

LL developed a google site that described the program expectations. Students were expected to complete an online module about mentorship and to meet with their mentor three times during the semester.

The online mentorship education module was required for the mentees and optional for mentors. It covered what mentoring is, stages of mentoring, how to get started, characteristics of effective and dysfunctional relationships, and ethical obligations. Three meetings were expected about one month apart. The goal for each meeting is listed below.

- Meeting 1 (by end of Feb): share interests and get to know one another.
- Meeting 2 (in March): student interviews their mentor for a leader interview paper assignment.
- Meeting 3 (April): Suggested a 'shadowing' experience occur.

In addition, students were asked to talk with their mentor to identify a leadership episode to author a case study on for the course. Students who did not participate in the mentoring program had the same assignment - they had to identify a rural leader on their own and find a leadership episode for a case study.

The mentoring program was deliberately set up to provide an inquiry experience. Students had to ask what kind of leader their mentor was and what leadership episode was relevant for a case study. The students were supported by the professor to engage in mentoring, but they had to be action oriented to set up the meetings, decide on a shadowing experience and direct their conversations. The experience was self-directed in that students had to sign up for the experience, indicate their preferences for a type of mentor, and engage in the relationship.

Process

We take a dialogue approach to examine how the mentoring program unfolded over the 15-week semester course. The student perspective is shared first and then the faculty member shares her perspective.

Student Perspective

Below, we reflect on our experience, along with data collected from our classmates through an online, anonymous survey. EP and JB surveyed the other mentees (n = 8) using Google forms. The responses were anonymous so students would not feel obligated to tailor their responses. Four students responded.

We first describe the briefing on mentoring and then reflect about our meetings with our mentor. Finally, we describe how the class speakers also enriched our mentoring experiences.

Training

Throughout this semester we worked towards understanding what leadership and the leadership triangle is. Mentoring one skill of effective leaders. Thus, part of the course curriculum, even if you did not participate in the mentoring program, was to learn what a mentor does and what mentorship is.

Everyone in the course, even if they were not participating in the mentoring program, took a 3-hour Mentoring Fundamentals Online Course developed by LL. This preparation had to be completed before our first mentor meeting and it helped us define what mentorship is and what mentors do. The course was instrumental in instructing us about what the mentor-mentee relationship was supposed to look like. In the mentor program, we worked through modules about communication, boundaries, and the ethical dilemmas that can be present in any mentorship.

Each module we completed had a specific focus with a mix of videos, readings, and interactive worksheets to complete. There were short quizzes at the end of each module to test our knowledge on the material.

The most important piece of information the training taught us is how to develop a healthy mentor relationship. We learned that mentorship is a process. This process will help the mentee reach their full potential and goals while learning from someone who has been there. A good mentor helps, supports, and guides us, the mentees, but does not tell us the exact steps to take. The key to developing a healthy mentor relationship rests in clear communication. JB notes, “the training taught me the importance of feeling comfortable with my mentor, while still maintaining a level of professionalism. This ensured that our discussions were not centered around our personal lives but focused on the goals we set for our mentorship.”

The peer survey showed that other students found the mentorship online training useful. One student said, “I learned many things about a different sector of mentorship that I never knew before.” Another student found the mentor training effective because it provided insight into what could be expected and how they could find a mentorship that was beneficial for them and the other person.

Meetings

We were required to meet with our mentors three times. However, if we chose to, we could meet with them more than that. The first session was dedicated to getting to know each other. The hour-long session included learning about what our mentors did and their backgrounds. During the meeting our mentors also learned about our goals and background stories.

Starting out in the mentoring program it was nerve racking to think about talking to someone over a zoom call that you had never met before. EP notes that, “while I knew this was a great opportunity to have a mentor who had been there before it was a scary thought to think about this.” EP was worried about how the whole process would work out and if it would even be beneficial. The other mentees had a lot of questions about the process of the program, and we too felt unclear on what the end goal was going to be. However, as the meetings progressed it seemed that we were able to define these goals and get clarity on how the process was going to work.

JB said that, “starting out in the mentoring program, I was nervous.” LL prepared us for this experience by having us take a variety of leader assessments such as the Big Five Personality Test, the FIRO-B, Tolerance for Ambiguity, Just World Scale, and the Poverty Test. After taking these assessments, JB noted she learned that her tolerance for ambiguity was low, hence why she was nervous about shadowing her mentor. In the first mentor meeting, JB noted that her nerves subsided as she was introduced to her mentor who worked rural health.

The second meeting was dedicated to asking our mentors questions about their leadership position to learn more about what kind of leader they were. The purpose of these questions was so we could determine for ourselves if they were a good leader. During this session we learned about their job, what they do, and how they delegate.

The last session was the shadowing experience, which looked different for every student. The shadowing experience was the time for mentees to see what their mentors did within their daily lives.

Overall, the meetings helped us to learn if we were interested in our mentor’s career field. These meetings were helpful to learn more about opportunities that could help with our futures. EP looked forward to her meeting sessions with her mentor because she said, “he always gave helpful advice about career options and life in general.” The meetings helped students connect to their mentors on a more personal level rather than just reading about them and connecting through email. The zoom meetings gave mentees a way to connect to them personally.

It was a great experience to be able to shadow these different leadership roles. It gave mentees insight into mentor’s meetings or daily work as a leader. EP was able to sit in on a meeting with rural leaders connected with her mentor. In this weekly meeting the leaders discuss issues, such

as how to facilitate conflicts involving the police versus the community, that are taking place in their community. EP observed that, “it was nice to see how these sessions went and be able to see how my mentor leads his followers to try and help them resolve these problems, in a way that is helpful to everyone in the situation and make sure everyone is represented.”

In JB’s mentor meetings she asked questions about her mentor’s career. JB used meetings to better understand how her mentor’s current position shaped her as a leader by asking about the challenges she has faced, how she grew her tolerance of ambiguity, why resilience has been important to her, what skills she thinks effective leaders should have, the leader figures who inspired her, and even what she has done when faced with working for a toxic or derailed leader. JB noted that, “creating a dialogue with my mentor about these topics of interest helped us share meaningful conversations that focused on her lived experiences and how those could impact and help me continue to grow as a leader throughout undergrad.”

JB said that during the shadowing experience, “I learned so much from listening to her [mentor] and her team discuss the tasks at hand.” It was helpful to hear the content of the meeting and how it was structured. The meeting concluded with an open discussion of ideas. Her mentor implements a strategy called the quad chart to help organize the thoughts of her team. JB noted that “this strategy is something useful that I plan to implement into my leadership roles and is something I will carry with me throughout my time in college and then into the workforce.”

In attending this shadowing event with my mentor JB said, “my eyes were opened to the large amount of work she and her office tackle every day. Watching her team interact and collaborate to tackle the issues at hand was eye opening and I was able to learn how effective leaders conduct meetings and work together to accomplish the tasks at hand.”

JB noted that, “overall, my mentorship experience altered the way I viewed mentorship as a whole.” JB recalled her mentorship experience by saying, “to be completely honest, I was not expecting to learn as much as I did from my experience with my mentor. Going into this experience, I thought mentorship was purely a relationship between me and my superior who would tell me exactly how to navigate life. However, through my experience, I learned that mentorship is reciprocal. While I learned a plethora of information about her job and her leadership style, she also said I taught her a number of things. That reciprocal relationship I formed with my mentor is what made my mentorship experience so meaningful.”

The peer survey echoed JB and EP’s experiences. The other mentees reported that they found value in the experience and believed it will be a long-lasting mentor relationship. One student shared, “my mentor was excited and eager to share advice with me as well as helping me achieve my goals. She has gone out of her way to assist me with leadership as well as classes. Establishing this kind of connection has been amazing.”

Further, the other mentees reported their view of the program changed from the beginning to the

end of the semester. In the survey responses students reported that they, “felt iffy about it at first but ended up enjoying it.” Another student said that, “going into their mentorship, they didn’t know anything about mentorship,” but now understands its benefits. Another response indicated that the student used to view mentorship as a teaching moment and something that was one-sided. Now, this person saw mentorship as a partnership and both sides should benefit from it.

Speakers as Mentors

In addition to our individual mentors, throughout the semester JB and EP note, “we had multiple guest speakers come to discuss leadership with us. These leaders each held different positions, but all offered advice that assisted emerging leaders in developing their skills. We learned that each speaker had mentors and were mentors to others, which enhanced their leadership skills.” As mentees, these leaders learned the fundamentals of leadership and how to lead more effectively those around them. As mentors, these leaders equipped mentees with the necessary skills to succeed in completing the tasks at hand. JB noted, “learning from these guest speakers was important in helping me fully understand the value found within mentorship.”

Faculty Perspective

Ten of the 15 students in the class signed up to participate in the mentoring program and expressed enthusiasm for the opportunity. All the students in the class were asked to take the online mentorship course to learn about mentoring and all of them completed it. Mentorship was positioned as a leadership skill, which was why it was part of the content of the leadership course. The mentorship course was optional for the mentors. Three mentors signed up but none of them completed the course.

LL checked in with the mentees during class to make sure they had emailed their prospective mentor to set up a meeting. During class everyone indicated they were on track. However, LL later learned from the NC Rural Center that one of the students had not connected their mentor. LL was surprised that, “the students seemed excited but a little confused about what they were supposed to do at the beginning.” LL felt the google site presented a clear structure for the meetings and how the mentoring experience aligning with class assignments to provide an inquiry learning experience. For example, topics and outcomes were suggested for each meeting. However, it took two meetings for students to see the connection between meeting with their rural leader mentor and the assignments. LL observed that, “it made it easier for students to do the leader interview because the leader had already been selected for them and I didn’t have to approve (or disapprove) their selection of a leader to interview.”

The leader interview paper showed LL that the students had connected with the mentors and were learning about how leadership knowledge we discussed in class translated to practical rural leadership experiences. However, LL did not track closely enough to make sure the leader they interviewed was their mentor, which is why she missed that one student had not connected with their mentor.

As students worked on the case study it became clear they were more engaged with their mentor. There were four case discussion assignments in class, but it was challenging for students to envision how they could write a case study about a rural leadership episode.

LL suggested an optional shadowing experience but felt it was unlikely to occur given the pandemic. However, LL was amazed at how many students were able to arrange an in-person or virtual shadowing experience; all of which seemed to resonate with the students. Some students were quite excited about their shadowing experiences and shared that they plan to stay in touch with their mentor after the class ends. One student sent LL an unsolicited email about her shadowing experience. Below is an excerpt from the email:

It was an experience that I enjoyed more than words can express. I learned so much from [my mentor] and her team from the few hours that I spent with them and got to see first-hand what it really means to give back to a community in need. I will remember to take the lessons learned from that day with me throughout the rest of my life! I figured that you would be interested to know how my shadowing experience went :).

Overall, the RLM program seemed to be a positive experience for the students who participated in it. The mentorship required that they apply what they were learning in class about rural leadership. It was uncomfortable for them at times but most of the students appeared to build genuine, close relationships even during the short, three-month period.

Challenges

The students identified two sets of challenges: COVID-19 limited face-to-face contact and it was difficult to align calendars for meetings. The faculty member saw three challenges related to: a) supporting students getting started in the mentoring relationship; b) understanding how the class assignments would align with the mentoring experiences; and the COVID-19 challenges the students identified. Each challenge is discussed below, first by the students, then by the faculty member.

Student Perspective

JB and EP identified two challenges that were experienced by all student mentees. First, because of Covid-19 the meetings and shadowing experiences were online. This made it hard to connect with the mentors and get the full experience of the program. Several classmates felt awkward meeting online and it was challenging for them to have meaningful conversations with their mentor. JB and EP report that most students would have preferred to be able to meet in person with their mentor.

At the same time, having online meetings made it much easier to meet. JB and EP acknowledge the program would have likely been online anyway for ease. The students who were from NC were assigned to rural leaders in or near their hometown. Thus, it would have been possible for

some mentees to meet with their mentors when they might have been going home for a long weekend.

JB noted that she learned how to use Microsoft Teams. She met with her mentor once a month, January-March, and then attended a virtual meeting with her mentor and her leadership team in April. JB felt they connected on the surface but, “I deeply value face-to-face interactions, so having to meet with my mentor online was challenging.” She felt disconnected during the shadowing experience as no one had their cameras turned on and she missed out on seeing people’s facial expressions. Had there not been a pandemic she might have been able to attend the meeting face to face with others and made more connections.

Other students also felt the pandemic limited the mentoring experience. One student said it was not possible to shadow their mentor in person, so it was not possible to really “meet” her. Another student hated not being able to go to their mentor’s business, and that it was challenging not always being able to have big group discussions and collaborate with their mentor.

Second, it was a challenge to match up mentee and mentor schedules. EP was conflicted as a possible shadowing experience conflicted with the class time for this course. It took her a while to seek permission to miss class. JB for example, found it easy to procrastinate work from her other classes, which made it more difficult to schedule meetings with her mentor at times. However, this challenge forced her to better manage her time, and ultimately made her a more organized student, which is important in effective leadership.

Faculty Perspective

There were three challenges from LL’s perspective. First, LL realized more support was needed to help students connect with mentors and discover what was interesting to them to explore in a self-directed manner. LL sometimes split the class so that she could talk with the students in the mentoring program directly without wasting the other students’ time.

Second, it was hard for many of the mentees to identify a leadership episode for a case study. Some students struggled to find the right case that would have sufficient evidence to support the development of the case. Some students only relied on their mentor’s perspective at first and learned that would be insufficient. Some of the leadership episodes were sensitive in that they covered problems that were still happening. It can be hard to be factual about episodes that have not yet ended. LL felt she will provide more information in the future about the need for evidence for the case studies.

Third, students desired the opportunity to meet in person at times with their mentor. For some students their mentor was near their hometown or within an hour drive of the campus. As the university had face to face classes during this time it was hard for students to be virtual with their mentors. They desired a close connection. There is value in seeing where their mentor worked,

and LL hopes that can be an option in the future.

Concerns

In addition to the challenges noted above there were two types of concerns we identified. First, students were unsure at times if they could raise issues about mentor conflicts with class time. They were not sure how to discuss these conflicts with LL.

Second, LL was concerned about the university reputation if a mentoring relationship does not work out. For example, the student who did not contact a mentor was a concern. LL worried it might negatively influence the desire of the NC Rural Center to identify future mentors.

Recommendations

Based on the student feedback the RLM program was a successful pilot. Students learned more about mentoring and leadership through engagement with a leader in a rural community. LL plans to implement the mentoring program in future course offerings. However, there are three recommendations for future iterations of this program. These recommendations may also be useful to others considering a mentoring program as part of an inquiry experience.

The first recommendation is to change the number of meetings to be biweekly rather than monthly, even if the meetings are shorter. Mentees felt it was difficult to assess their mentor's leadership style and tendencies when you meet only once a month. LL plans to require monthly meetings but recommend bi-weekly meetings.

A second recommendation is to add 'checkpoint' assignments to make sure that mentees are on track and clear about expectations. Students may be better prepared to write their community leader paper and their case study at the end of the semester with this additional support. These checkpoints will also let LL know if mentees and mentors are connecting. The checkpoints could be added in the course learning management system as questions for mentees that are relevant to the expectations for that month.

The third recommendation is to provide guidance that students need to discuss the shadowing experience at the first meeting. And, if possible, identify potential class or timing conflicts at that first meeting so they can be resolved early in the semester. This support would give students time to talk with professors and their mentors to create a solution if the shadowing experience conflicts with class time.

Conclusion

It is difficult to teach leadership to students who may not have a lot of experience as leaders or as followers. This paper examined a rural leadership mentoring program that provided an inquiry experience in a leadership course.

LL felt it was important to connect the mentorship experience with class assignments to support learning as inquiry. It was as not time-intensive to run the program in this manner, but it was critical to have an organization to identify the right mentors.

The mentorship provided an inquiry experience where students had to understand the material sufficiently to complete two course assignments. First, students needed to interview and reflect on their mentor leader's skills and traits, their interactions with followers, and how the environment influenced their leadership. Second, the students had to ask questions to make sense of a leadership episode that had occurred in their mentor's rural community and author a mini-case study about it. The students had to ask good questions to identify the right leadership episode, to decide what perspective to take in writing up the case study, and to provide evidence along with questions (and possible correct answers) that would go along with a case analysis. LL reported that the cases completed by students with mentors were richer and more in depth than those completed by students without mentors.

EP and JB felt that the mentorship opportunity was a great experience during college to gain insight on the real world and learn how to be a leader in actual scenarios. EP felt the RLM program helped her and other mentees to learn how to communicate more effectively with others. She is now more confident in how to talk with people who are older than her from a learning perspective. JB also reported a gain in confidence in her leadership skills. Like other students, she felt that being paired with a mentor, who was working to serve underserved communities, was very meaningful. She noted, "learning from my mentor was eye opening and has helped me understand the aspects of leadership we discussed in class, and how they apply them to the workforce and other aspects of life outside of college."

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